

Linnæus University

Monthly Report July 2025 SENTINEL Wild Birds

Söderquist, P., Byrne, A., Lewis, N., van Toor, M., Waldenström, J., &
SENTINEL Wild Birds Consortium

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SUMMARY REPORT

1. OVERVIEW

SENTINEL Wild Birds aims to enhance the understanding of highly pathogenic avian influenza (HPAI) virus dynamics in wild bird populations by conducting active surveillance at key locations in and near Europe. These locations are divided into the following surveillance nodes: Node 1 Gulf of Finland (Finland, Estonia), Node 2 Southern Baltic Sea (Sweden, Latvia, Lithuania, Poland), Node 4 Eastern Black Sea (Georgia), Node 6 Lake Constance (Germany, Austria, Switzerland), Node 7 Veneto Region (Italy), Node 8 Camargue (France), and Node 9 Gulf of Cadiz (Spain). This monthly summary provides an update on sampled wild birds as part of an early warning system to support wildlife management and disease prevention efforts. The data in this report are based on previously unpublished samples collected from April 2025 to July 2025, along with a few backlogged samples from Switzerland in February and March 2025.

2. RESULTS

2.1 DATA COLLECTION

Since the last monthly report (published on 27th of June 2025; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15754338>), and as of 15th July 2025, test results have been submitted for 1,241 samples taken from 747 individuals representing 19 taxa across 6 nodes in and near Europe (Table 1). Of the 1,241 collected samples, 578 (47 %) were tracheal/oropharyngeal swabs, 525 (42 %) were cloacal swabs, 67 (5 %) faecal samples, 31 (2 %) blood samples, 31 (2 %) combined swabs (choana + cloacal), and 9 (<1 %) mussel samples. Of all samples, none were positive for avian influenza virus (Figure 1; Table 2).

The most sampled species were yellow-legged gull (260 individuals), Armenian gull (204 individuals), black-headed gull (67 individuals), glossy ibis (65 individuals), and white stork (51 individuals) (Table 1).

TABLE 1 Most recently sampled individuals in the SENTINEL Wild Birds project. Total number of individuals (including mussels) sampled in the wild, as well as number of individuals tested positive for avian influenza virus in the respective country. The table includes previously unpublished samples from February to July 2025.

Group/species	Node 2 Lithuania		Node 4 Georgia		Node 6 Austria		Node 6 Switzerla		Node 7 Italy		Node 8 France		Node 9 Spain		Total	
	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.
<i>Waterfowl</i>																
Mute Swan	0	0	0	0	1	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0
Greylag Goose	0	0	0	0	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	0
Egyptian Goose	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
Duck (unknown species)	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	0
Mallard	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	0
<i>Cormorants</i>																
Great Cormorant	2	0	0	0	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	12	0
<i>Storks & Ibises</i>																
White Stork	0	0	0	0	49	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	51	0
Glossy Ibis	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	65	0	65	0
<i>Raptors</i>																
Red Kite	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0
<i>Rails</i>																
Eurasian Coot	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
<i>Cranes</i>																
Common Crane	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
<i>Larids</i>																
Black-headed Gull	0	0	0	0	62	0	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	67	0
Common Gull	2	0	0	0	2	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	0
European Herring Gull	26	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	26	0
Yellow-legged Gull	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	259	0	0	0	260	0
Armenian Gull	0	0	204	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	204	0
Common Tern	0	0	0	0	9	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9	0
<i>Others</i>																
Mussels	0	0	0	0	0	0	9	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9	0
Unknown species	0	0	0	0	0	0	13	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	13	0
Total	31	0	204	0	141	0	45	0	2	0	259	0	65	0	747	0

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FIGURE 1 Sample sites in the SENTINEL Wild Birds project. Sample sites for the 747 individuals (including mussels) sampled in seven countries in and near Europe. The figure includes previously unpublished samples from February to July 2025.

TABLE 2 Most recently collected samples in the SENTINEL Wild Birds project. Total number of collected samples as well as number of samples positive for avian influenza virus, in the respective country. The table includes previously unpublished samples from February to July 2025.

Group/species	Node 2 Lithuania			Node 4 Georgia			Node 6 Austria			Node 6 Switzerland			Node 7 Italy			Node 8 France			Node 9 Spain			Total		
	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI
<i>Waterfowl</i>																								
Mute Swan	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0
Greylag Goose	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	0
Egyptian Goose	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
Duck (unknown species)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	0
Mallard	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	0
<i>Cormorants</i>																								
Great Cormorant	2	0	0	0	0	0	30	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	32	0	0
<i>Storks & Ibises</i>																								
White Stork	0	0	0	0	0	0	95	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	99	0	0
Glossy Ibis	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	130	0	0	130	0	0
<i>Raptors</i>																								
Red Kite	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0
<i>Rails</i>																								
Eurasian Coot	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
<i>Cranes</i>																								
Common Crane	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
<i>Larids</i>																								
Black-headed Gull	0	0	0	0	0	0	62	0	0	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	67	0	0
Common Gull	2	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	0
European Herring Gull	26	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	26	0	0
Yellow-legged Gull	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	518	0	0	0	0	0	519	0	0
Armenian Gull	0	0	0	304	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	304	0	0
Common Tern	0	0	0	0	0	0	9	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9	0	0
<i>Others</i>																								
Mussels	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9	0	0
Unknown species	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	13	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	13	0	0
Total	31	0	0	304	0	0	209	0	0	45	0	0	4	0	0	518	0	0	130	0	0	1241	0	0

A weekly compilation of all 15,278 samples (positive and negative; including previously published), collected at each node from August 2024 to July 2025, can be seen in Figure 2.

FIGURE 2 Weekly summary of collected samples in the SENTINEL Wild Birds project. In total, 15,278 samples (negative samples in blue; avian influenza virus-positive samples in orange) have been collected at seven nodes between August 2024 and July 2025, yielding 1,040 samples positive for avian influenza virus, including 24 samples positive for HPAI virus. The figures also include samples published in previous reports.

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2.2 GENOMICS SUMMARY

Since the last report was published on 27th of June 2025 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15754338>), and as of 15th July 2025, no new sequences have been generated from samples positive for avian influenza virus. The latest and previous Nextstrain builds are available on the SENTINEL Wild Birds Group (<https://nextstrain.org/groups/SentinelWildBirds>).

3. CONCLUSION

During spring, the sample activity has been low in most countries. However, from late May and onwards, sampling of mostly breeding gull colonies as well as storks and ibises at several nodes has increased, yielding 1,241 analysed samples from 747 individuals, and 19 different taxa. Also, the geographical coverage is good with collected samples from seven countries. However, none of the samples collected during the recent reporting period tested positive for avian influenza virus.

As breeding colonies, especially those of gulls, can facilitate rapid virus transmission if infected individuals are present, as observed in the 2023 outbreak in a black-headed gull and tern colony in United Kingdom (Coffey & Verspoor, 2025), it remains crucial to maintain vigilant surveillance during this period.

REFERENCES

Coffey, P., & Verspoor, R. S. (2025). Case study of the impact of an outbreak of high pathogenicity avian influenza (HPAI) on a seabird colony in Flintshire, Wales, United Kingdom. *Bird Study*, 1-9.

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